

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PROBLEM SOLVING METHODOLOGY IN PHYSICS

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Abstract – This article, in the process of solving problems in physics, the logical thinking and creativity of students will be developed, the basic nature of physical phenomena will be more widely explained, they will have a deeper understanding of the practical application of the laws of physics, they will get acquainted with the function, device and principles of operation of many physical measuring instruments, acquire skills and qualifications to work with them. Also, tasks can instill in students diligence, courage, will and character, information about a problem, usually physical, which is solved on the basis of logical conclusions, mathematical operations, laws and methods of physics or through experiments.

Keywords – solving problems, physics, Classification of problems, physical problem.

Development of methodologies

In our country, the introduction of new state education standards based on the competence approach imposes a number of urgent tasks on the shoulders of secondary school teachers. At the same time, the introduction of 11-year secondary education in schools from the 2017-2018 school year, in turn, has created new needs for teacher training. At the moment, the conditions that have arisen and the form, content and mechanisms of the teachers' professional development require to be reconsidered and the appropriate changes to be made to this process. In particular, based on the above needs and the problems facing them, there is a need to improve the content and forms of training of physics teachers [1,2,3].

The uniqueness of the content of physics. Basic concepts and relations, definitions, problems, formulas and laws in the school physics course. Modern educational technologies and methods of teaching physics: 1) methods of scientific research (observation, experiment, comparison, analogy, analysis and synthesis, generalization, abstraction, concretization and classification), 2) teaching methods (explanatory-demonstration, demonstration, work with books, reproductive, heuristic (educational discovery), problem situation, research, project method, case study method, lecture, story, oral guidance, explanation, interview methods, practical training, laboratory work), 3) methods of drawing conclusions (induction, deduction and analytical method) [4,5,6].

In the process of solving physics problems, students' logical thinking expands and their creative abilities develop. They have a wider

understanding of the fundamental nature of physical phenomena, and a deeper understanding of the practical application of the laws of physics. They get acquainted with the function, structure, principles of operation of many physical measuring instruments, and acquire the skills and qualifications to work with them. Also, the issues educate hard work, courage, will and character in students. According to the analysis of many methodical literatures, a problem that is solved with the help of logical conclusions, mathematical operations and laws and methods of physics, or with the help of experiments, is usually called a physical problem.

Solving a problem posed in a physical problem consists in solving a problem. 2. Methods of solving physics problems Classification of problems: All problems given in physics problem sets are classified according to different bases. For example, according to the level of complexity of the problems, simple problems, more difficult problems, problems that are less familiar than those described in the problem conditions, textbooks and lessons, problems that students can use to gain new knowledge. Depending on the content of the problems, they can be related to mechanics, molecular physics, electricity and so on. We know that such a division is conditional, because information from several departments of physics is often used in the context of one problem [7,8,9].

It is also classified into issues that have a polytechnic content, are aimed at the development of creative abilities, and contain information of a historical nature. According to the solution methods, the problems are divided into qualitative,

experimental, graphic and creative problems. Such a division is also conditional, because in solving experimental problems, we use verbal reasoning, graphs, and calculations.

However, each of these issues is different in content and complexity. The solutions to these problems are focused on a specific goal and have methods of solution [10].

Qualitative problems: Problems solved by logical thinking, relying on physical laws, physical formulas, are called qualitative 117 problems. Arithmetic calculations are not performed in problems of this type. The methodological advantages of qualitative questions are many. This method of solving problems based on the laws of physics, which consists in drawing logical conclusions, serves as an excellent school of thought.

Qualitative problems clearly explain physical phenomena and their laws to students, teach them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, cultivate the right attitude to computational problems, teach them to solve any problem, to start analyzing its physical content. Questions related to quality are given in order to strengthen the material learned in the lesson. We know that in the hydrodynamics department of physics, qualitative problems are mainly solved. Quantitative issues are hardly solved in this section.

Quality issues are diverse in terms of theme, content and complexity, that is, there are simple and complex quality issues. Examples of qualitative problems and methods of solving them are fully presented in the literature.

Experimental problems: One of the most effective ways to connect theory with practice is to solve experimental problems. A characteristic feature of experimental problems is that laboratory or demonstration experiments are used to solve them. In the process of solving experimental problems, the activity and independence of students increases [2,4,6].

Because they do not get the necessary information to solve the problem from the textbook, from the set of problems, but from the physical measurements they make. Another advantage of experimental problems is that these problems cannot be solved without sufficient thought, that is, the phenomena that occur in the experiment must be widely discussed by the students.

Because in experimental problems, as in laboratory work, the theory is not given, and the procedure for performing the work is not shown. It is enough to provide the necessary equipment and materials and ask for the information to be found.

As we said above, students will learn from a series of thoughts and opinions, what kind of physical phenomenon is involved in the experiment, what kind of physical law is used. Finally, they derive the final expression for the physical quantity to be found in the experimental problem. Analyzing the expression, they get the quantities needed to solve the problem by direct measurement.

Let's see what has been said in the following simple experimental problem: Determine the period of oscillation of a mathematical pendulum fixed on a tripod using a scale ruler, a barbell circle, and a stopwatch. Teachers can assign some lab work and problems from problem sets as experimental problems, or creative teachers can create experimental problems themselves and recommend them for students to solve [1,3,5].

Graphical problems: Graphical problems are of great general and polytechnic importance. In the process of solving graphic problems, 118 students thoroughly learn the basics of physics. In the process of solving graphic problems in class and in the process of doing homework independently, students see in practice the interrelationships of physics and mathematics. Graphic problems also develop students' thinking skills. All sections of the physics course have graphical problems of practical importance.

In the simplest form, the problems consisting of graphs of connection of two physical quantities are called graphical problems. In some cases, the graph is given in the condition of the problem, in some cases, it is necessary to make graphs based on the results based on the condition of the problem. The algorithm for solving graphic problems is as follows: if a graph of the connection between physical quantities is given, it is necessary to carefully read and understand the graph and study the character of the connection in a separate part.

Using the scale on the drawing, you need to find the values of the quantities you are looking for on the abscissa and ordinate axes. In cases where the connection graph is not given, the graph is created according to the condition of the problem or the result obtained from the problem. For this,

coordinate axes are drawn, certain scales corresponding to each physical quantity are selected, tables are drawn up if necessary, and then corresponding points are placed on the abscissa and ordinate axes corresponding to the plane on which the coordinate axes are located.

By connecting these points, a graph of the connection between physical quantities is made, and conclusions are drawn by analyzing it. You can read about the importance of the graphical method in teaching physics and the exercises and problems related to the graph. Creative problems in physics: It is agreed that problems for which the solution algorithm is unknown are called "creative problems". The conditions of such problems are masked: givens are missing, givens are redundant, or physical data from the field necessary for the solution of the problem are not given at all.

When solving creative problems from physics, the first step is to explain the phenomenon, that is, it is necessary to answer the question why. In the second stage, the question of how to implement real events that meet the requirements is answered. Let's turn to the mechanical vibrations section of physics [10, 11, 12].

The study of mechanical vibrations is carried out with the help of laboratory devices and on the basis of solving problems. However, the issues related to this department are different: theoretical, practical and technical, which require a creative approach from the student. Therefore, in this topic, examples of solving a number of non-traditional and non-standard problems are presented:

1. How long does it take for a material point moving in harmonic oscillation according to the sine law to move half the amplitude distance from the equilibrium state? The oscillation period is 24 s and the initial phase is zero.

Solution: Equation of harmonic motion

$x = A \sin \omega t$ or $x = A \sin \frac{2\pi}{T} t$. According to the condition $x = \frac{A}{2}$ when $\sin \frac{2\pi}{T} t = 0,5$. From this $\frac{2\pi}{T} \cdot t = \frac{\pi}{6} \rightarrow t = \frac{T}{12} = 2s$.

If the oscillations occur with cosine law, $\cos \frac{2\pi}{T} t = 0,5 \rightarrow \frac{2\pi}{T} \cdot t = \frac{\pi}{3} \quad t = \frac{T}{6} = 4s$.

Therefore, the answer depends on the pattern of oscillation, and it is necessary to specify the pattern of oscillation in the questions and test tasks [13, 14, 15].

2. The initial phase of harmonic oscillations is zero. During what part of the period of the oscillation is its speed equal to half of its maximum speed?

Solution: Equation of harmonic oscillations $x = A \sin \omega t$ is its speed is equal to $v = \dot{x} = A \omega \cos \omega t = v_{\max} \cdot \cos \frac{2\pi}{T} t$.

According to the condition $v = 0,5v_{\max}$ for being $\cos \frac{2\pi}{T} t = 0,5$ and therefore will be equal to

$$\frac{2\pi}{T} t = \frac{\pi}{3} \Rightarrow t = \frac{T}{6}$$

If the oscillations occur according to the laws of cosines, will be equal to $\frac{2\pi}{T} t = \frac{\pi}{6}$ or $t = \frac{T}{12}$.

3. $\nu = 2 \text{ Hz}$ a material point moving in harmonic oscillation with frequency $t = 0$ моментда $x_0 = 6 \text{ sm}$ situation $v_0 = 14 \text{ sm/s}$ passes quickly. Determine the amplitude of oscillation.

Solution: If the equation of motion of harmonic oscillation is in the form, its velocity will be equal to $v = \dot{x} = A \omega \cos(\omega t + \varphi_0)$. $t = 0$ at the moment $x_0 = A \sin \varphi_0$ and will be equal to $v_0 = A \omega \cos \varphi_0$. Here φ_0 - initial phase.

$\cos \varphi_0 = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \varphi_0} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{x_0^2}{A^2}}$ and $\omega = 2\pi\nu$ considering that, $v_0 = A \cdot 2\pi\nu \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{x_0^2}{A^2}}$ we form the equation.

This equation $v_0^2 = 4\pi^2\nu^2 A^2 - 4\pi^2\nu^2 x_0^2$ from it by writing in the form A we define:

$$A^2 = \frac{v_0^2}{4\pi^2\nu^2} + x_0^2 \quad \text{or} \quad A = \sqrt{\frac{v_0^2}{4\pi^2\nu^2} + x_0^2}$$

Putting numerical values, $A = 6,39 \text{ sm}$ equal to

4. The point is at the same time $x = A_1 \cos \omega t$ and $y = A_2 \cos(t + \tau)$ performs

two harmonic oscillations occurring in mutually perpendicular directions represented by equations. In this $A_1 = 4 \text{ sm}$, $A_2 = 8 \text{ sm}$, $\omega = \pi \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\tau = 1 \text{ s}$. Find the equation of the trajectory of the point and determine its motion graph.

Solution: $x = A_1 \cos \omega t$ and $y = A_2 \cos \omega(t + \tau) = A_2(\cos \omega t \cdot \cos \omega \tau - \sin \omega t \cdot \sin \omega \tau)$ from Eqs t by eliminating t , we determine the trajectory equation: $\cos \omega t = \frac{x}{A_1}$ and

$$\sin \omega t = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \omega t} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{A_1^2}}; \omega = \pi$$

and $\tau = 1 \text{ s}$ considering that

$$y = A_2 \left(\frac{x}{A_1} \cdot \cos \pi - \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{A_1^2}} \cdot \sin \pi \right) = -\frac{A_2}{A_1} x$$

$A_2 = 8 \text{ sm}$ and $A_1 = 4 \text{ sm}$ for being $y = -2x$, that is, the resulting motion trajectory consists of a straight line.

5. A thin ring (obruh) hanging on a nail driven horizontally into the wall vibrates in a plane parallel to the plane of the wall. Ring radius $R = 30 \text{ sm}$. Calculate the oscillation period T of the ring [16,17].

Solution: The oscillation period of a physical pendulum $T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{I}{mga}}$ is equal to Here I is the

moment of inertia about the hinge point of the bolt, $I = I_0 + ma^2 = mR^2 + mR^2 = 2mR^2$ is equal to a - is the distance from the suspension point to the center of mass of the obruch, $u a = R$ is equal to

$$\text{In that case } T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mR^2}{mga}} = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{2R}{g}}$$

will be equal to $R = 30 \text{ sm} = 0,3 \text{ m}$ for being

$$T \approx 6,28 \sqrt{\frac{0,6}{10}} \approx 1,54 \text{ s} . \text{ Answer: } T \approx 1,54 \text{ s}$$

6. A load of 0.5 kg is hung on a rubber with a length of 40 cm and a radius of 1 mm. Young's modulus for rubber $3 \cdot 10^6 \text{ Pa}$ if, determine the period of vertical oscillation of the load.

Solution: Hooke's law for elastic deformation of rubber $\frac{\Delta l}{l} = \frac{1}{E} \cdot \frac{F}{S}$ is written in

the form From this $F = \frac{E \cdot S}{l} \Delta l$ and $F = k \Delta l$ is

the elastic coefficient of the spring $k = \frac{E \cdot S}{l}$ will

be equal to Here $S = \pi R^2$ - the cross-sectional surface of the rubber. Then the period of oscillation of the load

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{k}} = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m \cdot l}{E \cdot \pi R^2}}$$

$$T = 6,28 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{0,5 \cdot 0,4}{3 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 3,14 \cdot 10^{-6}}} \approx 0,91 \text{ s} .$$

Answer: $T \approx 0,91 \text{ s}$.

7. Mass $m = 60 \text{ g}$ and length $l = 50 \text{ cm}$ to the stern ends of $m_1 = 70 \text{ g}$ and $m_2 = 90 \text{ g}$ Two balls of mass g are mounted and suspended so that they can oscillate about a horizontal axis passing through the center of the boom. Determine the period of small-amplitude oscillations of the stern.

Solution: Oscillation period of the system

$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{I_0}{Mga}}$ determined by the formula. Here

$I_s = I_1 + I_2 + I$ - the moment of inertia of the system, M is the total mass of the system, a - the distance from the suspension point to the center of gravity and we define it as follows:

$$m_1 g \left(\frac{l}{2} + a \right) + m \cdot g a = m_2 g \left(\frac{l}{2} - a \right)$$

$$m_1 \cdot a + m \cdot a + m_2 \cdot a =$$

$$m_2 \cdot \frac{l}{2} - m_1 \cdot \frac{l}{2} \Rightarrow a = \frac{0,5l(m_2 - m_1)}{m_1 + m_2 + m}$$

Putting numerical values,

$$a = \frac{0,5 \cdot 0,5(90 - 70) \cdot 10^{-3}}{(70 + 90 + 60) \cdot 10^{-3}} \approx 0,023 \text{ m}$$

Moment of inertia of the system

$$I_s = m_1 (0,5l + a)^2 + m_2 (0,5l - a)^2 + \frac{1}{12} ml^2 + ma^2 \cdot$$

$$I_s = 5,2 \cdot 10^{-3} + 3,6 \cdot 10^{-3} + 1,3 \cdot 10^{-3} \approx 10,1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot$$

Oscillation period of the system

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{I_s}{(m_1 + m_2 + m)ga}} \approx 2,8 \text{ s} \cdot$$

Answer: $T \approx 2,8 \text{ s}$

8. Amplitude of harmonic oscillations $A = 2 \text{ cm}$ and its full energy $W = 3 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ J}$. How far a material point moves from its equilibrium position to it $F = 2,25 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ N}$ force acts.

Solving. Harmonic vibration is the full

energy of a moving material point $W = \frac{kA^2}{2}$ is

equal to The force acting on it at the moment in question $F = kx$ is equal to From these equations

$$x = \frac{F}{k} = \frac{F \cdot A^2}{2W} \text{ and from him}$$

$$x = \frac{2,25 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot (2 \cdot 10^{-2})^2}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot 10^{-7}} = 1,5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m or}$$

$$x = 1,5 \text{ sm} \cdot \text{ Answer: } x = 1,5 \text{ sm}$$

9. Pipe diameter $d = 1 \text{ cm}$, mass $m = 50 \text{ A}$ hydrometer with g is floating in water. The hydrometer was set free by submerging it in a little

water, and as a result, it began to vibrate harmonically. Find the period of these oscillations.

Solution: When the hydrometer is at rest, its weight is equal to the force acting on it: $mg = F_A = \rho Sgl$. x - in addition to the distance when the addition is dipped F_A - Archimedean force acts.

Then the equation of motion of the hydrometer $m\ddot{x} + F_A = 0, F_A = \rho S \cdot x \cdot g$ for

$$\text{being } a = \omega^2 x = \frac{F_A}{m} \cdot x + \frac{\rho Sg}{m} x = 0 \text{ from}$$

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\rho g S}{m} \text{ and } \omega = \sqrt{\frac{\rho g S}{m}} = \frac{2\pi}{T}$$

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{\rho g S}} = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{4m}{\rho g \pi d^2}} = \frac{4}{d} \sqrt{\frac{\pi m}{\rho g}}$$

$$T = \frac{4}{10^{-2}} \sqrt{\frac{3,14 \cdot 5 \cdot 10^{-2}}{10^4}} =$$

$$0,4 \sqrt{3,14 \cdot 5} \approx 0,4 \cdot 3,96 \approx 1,6 \text{ s}$$

Answer: $T = 1,6 \text{ s}$

10. Mass $m = 1 \text{ kg}$ is the body drag coefficient $r = 0,05 \text{ kg/s}$ located in a viscous medium. The body is the uniqueness of each $k = 50 \text{ N/m}$ is held in equilibrium by two identical springs, and the springs are not deformed. When the body is displaced from the equilibrium position, it vibrates, and the period of oscillations when the amplitude of these oscillations is reduced by 2 times, the number of oscillations, the damping coefficient, the frequency of oscillations, the logarithmic decrement of oscillations θ be determined (Fig. 4.5).

Solution: Period of special oscillation
 $T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{k_1 + k_2}} = 6,28 \sqrt{\frac{1}{100}} = 0,628 \text{ s}$ will

be equal to And the frequency of oscillation
 $\nu = \frac{1}{T} = \frac{1}{0,628} \approx 1,59 \text{ Hz}$. Extinction

coefficient $\delta = \frac{r}{2m} = \frac{0,05}{2 \cdot 1} = 0,025 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is equal
 to Logarithmic decrement of fade
 $\theta = \delta T = 0,025 \cdot 0,628 = 1,57 \cdot 10^{-2}$. The

number of oscillations until the amplitude of the
 oscillation is reduced by 2 times N the

$\theta = \frac{1}{N} \ln \frac{x_1}{x_N}$ we determine from the formula:

$N = \frac{1}{\theta} \ln \frac{x_1}{x_N}$. According to the condition of the

matter $\frac{x_1}{x_N} = 2$ and $\ln 2 = 0,69$. Therefore

$$N = \frac{0,69}{1,57 \cdot 10^{-2}} \approx 44 \text{ times.}$$

Answer:

$T_0 = 0,628 \text{ s}$, $\nu = 1,59 \text{ Гц}$, $\delta = 0,025 \text{ с}^{-1}$, $\theta = 1,57 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ~~≈ 44~~ ≈ 44 times.

11. Uniqueness 20 H / M is hung on a spring
 $0,2 \text{ кг}$ find the amplitude of the forced
 oscillations of the mass load. The amplitude of the
 coercive force 2 H , and the frequency is 2 times
 higher than the natural frequency of load
 fluctuations ($\omega = 2\omega_0$). Extinction coefficient
 $\delta = 0,5 \text{ с}^{-1}$.

Solution: Amplitude of forced vibrations

$A = \frac{F_0}{m\sqrt{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)^2 + 4\delta^2\omega^2}}$ determined by the

formula. $\omega_0 = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$ and $\omega = 2\omega_0$ considering that

$$A = \frac{F_0}{m\sqrt{9\omega_0^4 + 16\delta^2\omega_0^2}} = \frac{F_0}{m\omega_0\sqrt{9\omega_0^2 + 16\delta^2}}$$

$$\omega_0 = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} = \sqrt{\frac{20}{0,2}} = 10 \text{ с}^{-1}, \text{ from the fact that}$$

$$A = \frac{2}{0,2 \cdot 10 \sqrt{900 + 4}} \approx 0,03 \text{ M.}$$

Answer: $A \approx 0,03 \text{ M}$.

12. Vibration system $\nu = 1000 \text{ Гц}$ the
 frequency attenuator is performing oscillations. If
 the resonant frequency $\nu_{pe3} = 998 \text{ Гц}$ is the
 frequency of the natural oscillations ν_0 let it be
 determined [18].

$$1) \omega = \sqrt{\omega_0^2 - 2\delta^2} = 2\pi\nu$$

$$2) \omega_r = \sqrt{\omega_0^2 - 2\delta^2} = 2\pi\nu_r$$

3) Squaring these equations from it ω_0^2 we
 define:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \omega_0^2 - \delta^2 &= 4\pi^2\nu^2 \\ \omega_0^2 - 2\delta^2 &= 4\pi^2\nu_r^2 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$\text{and } \omega_0^2 = 8\pi^2\nu^2 - 4\pi^2\nu_r^2$$

4) From the last equations $\omega_0 = 2\pi\nu_0$ taking
 into account that, we determine the frequency of
 special oscillations:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_0 &= \sqrt{2\nu^2 - \nu_r^2} = \sqrt{2 \cdot 10^6 - 998^2} = \\ &= \sqrt{1003996} = 1001,99 \approx 1002 \text{ Гц} \end{aligned}$$

Answer: $\nu_0 \approx 1002 \text{ Hz}$

13. $\delta = 400 \text{ с}^{-1}$ The resonant frequency of a
 system characterized by the damping coefficient is
 the frequency of its natural oscillations
 $\nu_0 = 1 \text{ КГц}$ let it be determined how much it
 differs from

Given

$$\delta = 400 \text{ с}^{-1}$$

$$\nu_0 = 1 \text{ Гц} = 1000 \text{ Гц}$$

$$\omega_{pe3} = ?$$

Solution: Cyclic frequency of resonant
 oscillation of the system $\omega_{pe3} = \sqrt{\omega_0^2 - 2\delta^2}$ is
 determined from the expression The natural
 frequency of the system $\omega_0 = 2\pi\nu_0 = 2000\pi$
 since is equal to

$$\omega_{pe3} = \sqrt{(2000\pi)^2 - 2(400 \text{ с}^{-1})^2} = 6,234 \cdot 10^3 \text{ с}^{-1}$$

will be equal to From him $v_{pe3} = \frac{\omega_{pe3}}{2\pi} = 996 \Gamma y$
equality follows.

Answer: $\Delta v = v_0 - v_{pe3} \approx 4 \Gamma y$

14. Length $l = 120 \text{ cm}$ A physical pendulum in the form of a thin straight rod with some center of mass of the rod a oscillates about a horizontal axis passing perpendicular to itself through a point at a distance. a At what value of will the oscillation period T be smallest?

Solution: The frequency of oscillation of a physical pendulum $v_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{mga}{I}}$ where I is the moment of inertia relative to the suspension point of the pendulum $T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{I}{mga}}$, $I_0 = \frac{1}{12} ml^2$ and $I = I_0 + ma^2$ considering the

$$I_0 = \frac{l^2}{12} m + ma^2 = m \left(\frac{l^2}{12} + a^2 \right),$$

$$v_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{mga}{I_0 + ma^2}}$$

will be When T is minimum v will be maximum and for him v_0 of a from the binding function to a the derivative of should be zero, i.e $\dot{v}_0 = 0$. In that case

$$\left[\left(\frac{mga}{I_0 + ma^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]' = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{mga}{I_0 + ma^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\frac{mg(I_0 + ma^2) - mga \cdot 2ma}{(I_0 + ma^2)^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{I_0 + ma^2}{mga}} \cdot \frac{mgI_0 + m^2 ga^2 - 2m^2 ga^2}{(I_0 + ma^2)^2} = 0$$

provided that the equation is satisfied

$$a^2 = \frac{I_0}{m} = \frac{\frac{1}{12} ml^2}{m} = \frac{1}{12} l^2$$

$$a = \frac{l}{\sqrt{12}} = \frac{120 \text{ cm}}{2\sqrt{3}} \approx 34,6 \text{ cm}$$

Answer: $a \approx 34,6 \text{ cm}$

15. Radius $r = 1 \text{ mm}$ and length $l = 1 \text{ m}$ hanging on a steel wire $R = 0,1 \text{ m}$ find the period of torsional oscillations of a ball of radius Shear modulus for steel $N = 80 \text{ GPa}$ and density $\rho = 7700 \text{ kg/m}^3$ take it as

Solution: Torsion modulus $D = \frac{\pi R^4}{2l} N$ is

determined from the formula and here N - displacement module. The oscillation period of the system is determined as follows:

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{I_0}{D}}, T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{\frac{2}{5} mR^2}{D}}$$

$$D = \frac{\pi R^4}{2l} N = \frac{3,14 \cdot 10^{-12}}{2 \cdot 1} \cdot 80 \cdot 10^9 = 12,56 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ H} \cdot \text{m}$$

$$m = \rho V = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \rho$$

$$T = 6,28 \sqrt{\frac{0,4 \cdot \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \cdot \rho R^2}{D}} = 6,28 \sqrt{\frac{1,6 \cdot 3,14 \cdot \rho \cdot R^5}{3D}}$$

Simplifying, we calculate by putting numerical values:

$$T = 6,28 \cdot R^2 \sqrt{\frac{1,6 \cdot 3,14 \cdot \rho \cdot R}{3D}} \approx 11 \text{ c}$$

Answer: $T \approx 11 \text{ c}$

16. Material point 3 occurring in a straight line at the same time $x_1 = 3 \cos t$ (1), $x_2 = 3 \cos(t + \pi/3)$ (2), $x_3 = 3 \sin(t + 7\pi/6)$

(3) consists of oscillations in the form, determine the amplitude of the resulting oscillations and its initial phase.

Solution: A material point participates in three harmonic vibrations. The resulting vibrations are also harmonic. To apply the current formula for adding vibrations, we transfer the equations of vibrations to the same trigonometric function: sine or cosine

$$x_3 = 3 \sin(t + 7\pi/6) = 3 \cos(t + 2\pi/3).$$

So, 3 vibrations: their amplitudes $A_1 = A_2 = A_3 = 3 \text{ cm}$, the cyclic frequencies are the same: $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = \omega_3 = 1 \text{ c}^{-1}$, initial

phases $\varphi_1 = 0, \varphi_2 = \frac{\pi}{3}, \varphi_3 = \frac{2\pi}{3}$ we need to

add the vibrations that are First, two oscillations can be added according to the theorem of cosines,

and its result can be added again according to the theorem of cosines.

But here it is convenient to use a vector diagram. In this case, we determine the amplitudes by adding. The length of the vectors is taken to the same scale and x the angle between the axis is equal to the initial phase. From the vector diagram

$\varphi = \frac{\pi}{3}$ is equal to and $A = 2A = 6 \text{ cm}$ will be

equal to Answer: $A = 6 \text{ cm}$ and $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{3}$.

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